

Understanding the Step by Step Approach in Child's Cognitive Development

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Abstract

The cognitive development process in a child is key to understanding the growth and development of a child. Indeed, the science of child development and early learning makes clear the complexity of working with children from infancy through the early elementary years. This study is set against this background and is guided by one research question and a single objective which is to identify the stage-by-stage cognitive process that takes place in a child from birth to adulthood. The study adopted Vygotsky's Socio-cultural theory as its framework of analysis and made use of secondary data drawn mainly from journals, textbooks and other online materials. Descriptive research design was employed for the study while content analysis was used to analyze the collected data. The study amongst others; found that cognitive development in children is a very gradual and serial process with one stage building on another and that at the sensorimotor stage a child is always fascinated by symbols and colours. Consequently, the study recommends, amongst others, that learning should be activity-based with schools providing a lot of toys and other instructional materials for kids and that both parents and caregivers should be sensitive to the development process of every child.

Keywords: *Child, Cognitive, Cognitive development, Development psychology*

1. Introduction

Cognitive development in education is a field that is vast and varied yet unified by certain themes and beliefs that are basic especially with regard to cognitive development in early childhood (Bjorklund, 2013). It analyses how children gradually develop conscious control over knowledge and behaviour and how all these happen in a social context (Bjorklund, 2013).

Recent advancement in cognitive development challenges some of the conventional views of how children learn and how they succeed in school; on the other hand, it also provides

theoretical underpinning and empirical support for some of the well-recognized ideologies and practices in early education. According to the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) (2014), children are already learning at birth, and they develop and learn at a rapid pace in their early years. This provides a critical foundation for lifelong progress, and the adults who care for and/or educate children from birth through age 8 bear a great responsibility for their health, development, and learning activities. This is because young children thrive when they have secure, positive relationships with adults who are knowledgeable about how to support their development and learning.

The science of child development and early learning makes clear the complexity of working with young children from infancy through the early elementary years. Studies have shown that early childhood is a time when developmental changes that can have profound and lasting consequences for a child's future take place. While people have long debated whether "nature" or "nurture" plays the stronger role in child development, scholars such as Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky proposed two of the critical theories of cognitive development with regard to how the thinking of children develops and changes from infancy to adulthood (Broderick & Blewitt, 2015).

To McLeod (2022), the theories and beliefs of Piaget and Vygotsky are similar in particular ways, yet different in some other ways. For instance, Piaget saw children as inquiring scientists who have an ability of learning by experimenting with their environment whilst Vygotsky regarded children as apprentices who have the ability of learning from other individuals with more experience. In addition, Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development suggests that children move through four different stages of intellectual development which reflect the increasing sophistication of children's thought and at each stage of development, the child's thinking is qualitatively different from the earlier stages, that is, each stage involves a different type of intelligence, while Vygotsky focused on themes providing a differing perspective in regard to development (Broderick & Blewitt, 2015).

Research has also shown that much more is going on cognitively, socially, and emotionally in young children – including infants – than scientists or care-givers and education professionals previously knew. Even in their very early years, children have started to learn about their world in sophisticated ways that are not always reflected in their outward behaviour. It is against this backdrop that this paper takes a critical look at the issues surrounding the step by step approach in child's cognitive development from infancy to adulthood. In attempting to achieve this objective, the paper sets for itself the question: what are the developmental stages of a child? Data for this study were collected through secondary sources and reviewed through schematic content analysis.

2. Conceptual Review

Child

Hart (1992) stated that there is no universal definition of who is a child, adolescent or youth and that chronological age is not a sufficient criterion for establishing operational definitions. This is because childhood is understood in very different ways in different cultural and social contexts.

Thus, childhood is a social and cultural construction, not merely a stage in physical and psychological development.

UNHCR (1994) defined “child” as anyone under the age of 18 unless, under applicable law. While this definition provides a point of common reference for international organisations, NGOs and governments; operational definitions in the field may differ. For example, International Save the Children Alliance (ISCA, 1996) states that the International Committee of the Red Cross defines a minor as “below 15 years of age and not being accompanied by an adult”. This is in contrast, with the UNHCR definition given earlier which sets “under 18” as the age for inclusion in family tracing services of persons called children. However, for the purpose of this work, we shall see a child as any person between the ages of 1-12 years.

Cognitive Development

To McLeod (2022), cognitive development represents the maturation of intellect and mental functions that influence thinking, reasoning, and problem solving. Scholars such as Piaget, Vygotsky, and Kohlberg contributed great understanding to the psychological study of cognitive development. Some of the areas influenced by them were the understanding of behaviors, thought organization, conception of reality by one’s experiences, cultural effects on cognitive development, guides for psychologist to change thought processes, social interaction on cognitive development, processes of moral development and moral realism.

To Developmental Psychology (2004), cognitive development is the construction of thought processes, including remembering, problem solving, and decision-making from childhood through [adolescence](#) to adulthood. Cognitive development refers to how a person perceives, thinks, and gains understanding of his or her world through the interaction of genetic and learned factors. Among the areas of cognitive development are information processing, intelligence, reasoning, language development, and memory. Cognitive development occurs through the interaction of innate capacities and environmental events, and children pass through a series of stages.

Historically, the cognitive development of children has been studied in a variety of ways. The oldest is through intelligence tests, such as the widely used Stanford Binet Intelligence Quotient (IQ) test first adopted for use in the United States by psychologist Lewis Terman (1877–1956) in 1916 from a French model pioneered in 1905 (Lindsey et al., 2016).

3. Methodology

Methodology has to do with the steps, procedures or sequence used in the collection of data and the method used in analyzing and measuring the generated data. This study adopted descriptive research design. This is because descriptive research is concerned with the collection of data for the purpose of describing and interpreting existing conditions, attitude, opinions, beliefs, social practices and relationships. Secondary data were employed for this study, hence data were gotten from sources such as textbooks, journals and seminar papers relating to cognitive development. Content analysis was used in analyzing and interpreting the collected data.

4. Theoretical Framework

Vygotsky's Socio-cultural theory

Reasoning *a priori*, it is obvious that cognitive development is a systematic process through which the child learns and as well build up new attitude and thinks. This then leads us to the theoretical foundation of this paper which is founded on the Vygotsky's Socio-cultural theory of cognitive development.

Theories of cognitive development seek to explain the dynamic processes through which human minds grow and change from infancy till throughout life. Cognition refers to capabilities including memory, thinking and reasoning, spatial processing, problem solving, language, and perception. Importantly, theories of cognitive development aim to explain mechanisms of change and development, rather than to merely describe the capabilities of children across ages or between children, adults, and aging populations.

Lev Vygotsky (1896–1934) opined that there is interplay between biological and environmental influences, though he drew influential attention to the role of caregivers and culture in the developmental environment. Vygotsky's theory underscored the role of social interaction, and, in particular, interaction with expert social partners, in supporting children's cognitive development. Of critical importance was his concept of the zone of proximal development (ZPD), which is the difference between what a learner can do on his or her own and what he or she can do with the assistance of someone who possesses more expertise (Lindsey et al., 2016). Vygotsky averred that children acquire knowledge by participating in cultural activities, such as preparing food, in which they observe and mimic, and eventually internalize what they see. This internalization process is mediated by the child's language use and involves cultural artifacts, tools, and icons (e.g., spoons and recipes for preparing food). Subsequent theorists continued to build on this model, emphasizing the role of the child's environment in development and privileging social factors over biological factors.

Extrapolating from the above theoretical construct and superimposing it on our present discourse, it is clear that the cognitive development process of a child is most times determined by the immediate environment and other social factors over the biological factors of a child. This is because with the child's continuous interaction with the internal and external environments, the child internalizes, mimic and eventually displays such characteristic and attitudes as it is learnt. We can therefore state that the environment influences the cognitive behaviour and development of a child. As children play and interact within a particular environment, they tend to become attached to entangle with and influenced by what they see, hear and feel.

The Cognitive Development Stages of a Child: An Overview

Developmental theory views cognition as a sequential and increasingly complex unfolding of biologically driven abilities. It was once believed that infants lacked the ability to think or form complex ideas and remained without cognition until they learned language. However, it is now known that babies are aware of their surroundings and interested in exploration from the time they are born. In fact, from birth, babies begin to actively learn; they gather, sort, and process information from around them using the data to develop perception and thinking skills.

To Blumberg et al. (2009), there are five basic fields of development. These fields are: (i) language (ii) visual-motor tasks (iii) fine motor development (iv) gross motor development, and (v) social behaviour. Different scholars have proposed different theories on the development of each field. At varying ages, children sequentially achieve abilities that become increasingly complex. These abilities may be mediated by two central features related to the concept of "executive" functioning. The first is increasing development of "working memory" and the second is the influence of "expertise." Children develop at varying rates, therefore, the exact age at which children develop skills is not necessarily predictive of their ultimate adult capabilities (i.e. children who begin to read at age 4 years may have similar outcomes as children who begin to read at age 7).

It is worthy to note that there are various theories and perspectives to understanding the step by step approach to the cognitive development of a child. These are proposed by scholars such as Arnold Gesell, Erik Erikson, Edgar A. Doll, Alfred Binet and Jean Piaget. In this regard, Hurley (2011) stated that Arnold Gesell proposed a "sequential" theory to development where each stage of development was a prerequisite for the next stage, Erikson took a "psychological view" of development and proposed a model made up of eight stages (known as the "Eight Stages of Man") that extended into adulthood - failure to master these stages result in difficulties; while Jean Piaget believed that children were active participants in learning. He viewed children as busy, motivated explorers whose thinking develops as they acted directly on the environment using their eyes, ears, and hands. Hurley (2011) also averred that to Piaget, between infancy and adolescence children move through four stages of development. Piaget devoted his life to epistemology, or how thoughts were transformed into a body of knowledge. His theory of cognitive development was inspired by observation of his three children from infancy.

In understanding the step by step approach to cognitive development in a child, this paper adopts the Piaget's cognitive development theory and the four factors that influence cognitive behavior which include: maturation of the nervous system, experience, social transmission of information or teaching and the equilibration (innate tendency for mental growth to progress toward increasingly complex and stable levels of organization).

McLeod (2022), avers that Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development suggests that intelligence changes as children grow. A child's cognitive development is not just about acquiring knowledge, the child has to develop or construct a mental model of the world (Piaget, 1936). At the center of Piaget's theory is the principle that cognitive development occurs in a series of four distinct, universal stages, each characterized by increasingly sophisticated and abstract levels of thought. These four stages, according to Piaget (1936), always occur in the same order, and each builds on what was learned in the previous stage. They are:

- i. Sensorimotor stage (Birth to 2 years of life)
- ii. Preoperational stage (Age 2 to 7 years)
- iii. Concrete operational stage (Age 7 to 11 years)
- iv. Formal operational stage (Age 12 years and above)(Adolescence)

The Sensorimotor Stage (Ages: Birth to 2 Years)

This stage can be further divided into the following six sub-phases, namely:

- (i) Uses of reflexes
- (ii) Primary circular reactions
- (iii) Secondary circular reactions
- (iv) Coordination of schemata and its application to new situation
- (v) Tertiary circular reactions
- (vi) Invention of new means through mental combination (Nkwocha et al., 1997, p. 44).

At birth, the child may not be able to talk, and so depends on his body for communication; there are also reflexes such as sucking and grasping; but the days pass by, he discovers there is a relationship between his action and effects and this will consequently lead him to repeat those actions that produce pleasurable results. With this, the child is now able to act intentionally. He also displays curiosity and enjoys novelty and bright colours. Beginning from about 8 months till the end of this period, the child achieves object permanence, the implication of which is that objects exist even when hidden from him. He can also search for these objects for a relatively short period of time if taken from him. He can also repeat the actions of another person at a later time; he is largely egocentric and more of a pre-moral person.

Hurley (2011) avers that at this stage, the infant learns about the world through their senses and through their actions (moving around and exploring its environment). During the sensorimotor stage a range of cognitive abilities develop; these include: object permanence; self-recognition; deferred imitation; and representational play. They relate to the emergence of the general symbolic function, which is the capacity to represent the world mentally.

McLeod(2022), states that during this stage the infant lives in the present. It does not yet have a mental picture of the world stored in its memory therefore it does not have a sense of object permanence. If it cannot see something then it does not exist. Towards the end of this stage the general symbolic function begins to appear where children show in their play that they can use one object to stand for another. Language starts to appear because they realise that words can be used to represent objects and feelings.

The Preoperational Stage (Ages: 2 - 7 Years)

This stage can be subdivided into two sub-stages, namely: (1) Preconceptual phase (2-4years) and the intuitive phase (4-7years). At this stage, the child begins to acquire language and uses words to represent symbols and things. Objects are also used to represent other objects, for instance, chairs are used as cars; toy phones are used as cell phones. Since the child is still dominated by what he sees and has not yet achieved reversibility, his reasoning is mono-causal and focused more on issues of prominence, for instance, a tall person is older than a shorter one (Nkwocha et al., 1997, p.45).

Toddlers and young children acquire the ability to internally represent the world through language and mental imagery. During this stage, memory and imagination are developing. Children at this age are egocentric, which means they have difficulty thinking outside of their

own viewpoints. A child's thinking is dominated by how the world looks, not how the world is. It is not yet capable of logical (problem solving) type of thought.

Infants at this stage also demonstrate animism - this is the tendency for the child to think that non-living objects (such as toys) have life and feelings like a person's. By 2 years, children have made some progress towards detaching their thought from physical world. However, they have not yet developed logical (or 'operational') thought characteristic of later stages.

The Concrete Operational Stage (Ages: 7 - 11 Years)

At this stage, the child begins to develop the ability for mental calculations leading to greater appreciation of numbers. Unlike the preceding stage, he can now understand the issue of serialization and reversibility. He now sees other's point of view as relevant in certain situations and thus gradually frees him from being the only important person at all times. He also shows mutual respect and cooperates with others in the achievement of desired objectives.

Piaget (1936), states that during this stage, children begin to think logically about concrete events; they can mentally reverse things (e.g. picture a ball of plastic returning to its original shape).

To McLeod (2022), the stage is called "concrete" because children can think logically much more successfully if they can manipulate real (concrete) materials or pictures of them. Piaget considered the concrete stage a major turning point in the child's cognitive development because it marks the beginning of logical or operational thought. This means the child can work things out internally in his head (rather than physically try things out in the real world).

Children can conserve number (age 6), mass (age 7), and weight (age 9). Conservation is the understanding that something stays the same in quantity even though its appearance changes. But operational thought can only be effective here if a child is asked to reason about materials that are physically present. Children at this stage will tend to make mistakes or be overwhelmed when asked to reason about abstract or hypothetical problems. The main goal at this stage is for a child to start working things out inside his head. This is called operational thought, and it allows kids to solve problems without physically encountering things in the real world.

The Formal Operational Stage (Ages: 12 Years and Over)

This stage is characterized by ability for abstract reasoning, formal logic, and the development of solutions to real and envisaged problems. At the formal operational stage, concrete operations are carried out on physical things whereas formal operations are carried out on ideas. Formal operational thought is entirely freed from physical and perceptual constraints. During this stage, Gopnik (2010) opines that adolescents can deal with abstract ideas (e.g. they no longer need to think about slicing up cakes or sharing sweets to understand division and fractions). They can follow the form of an argument without having to think in terms of specific examples. Adolescents can deal with hypothetical problems with many possible solutions. E.g. if asked "What would happen if money were abolished in one hour's time?" They could speculate about many possible consequences.

This stage sees emergence of scientific thinking, formulating abstract theories and hypotheses when faced with a problem; thus a milestone of this period is using symbols to understand abstract concepts. Not only that, McLeod (2022), adds that older kids and adults can also think about multiple variables and come up with hypotheses based on previous knowledge. Piaget believes that people of all ages develop intellectually, but he also believes that once a person reaches the formal operational stage, it's more about building upon knowledge, not changing how it's acquired or understood.

Implications of Piaget Theory of Cognitive Development

- (1) Sequel to the fact that cognitive development in children is a very gradual serial process with one stage building on another, then learning contents need to be introduced gradually too. The teacher should ascertain the level/stage a child has reached while designing his learning experiences.
- (2) It is advisable that since at the sensorimotor stage a child is always fascinated by symbols and colours, then a lot of toys should be provided at this level of learning so as to make learning very interesting (Epelle & Uriah, 2010, p.46).
- (3) Teachers, especially those at the preoperational level (nursery classes) should always endeavour to be good role models as children at this level are good imitators of adult behaviour. Good moral conduct by the pupils should also be openly rewarded.
- (4) At the concrete operational stage, classes should be taught with instructional materials and homework that will engage pupils' brain and make them reason in concrete terms given.
- (5) For the formal operational stage, higher order questions that will lead to independent thought by pupils should be given.

In summary, at every stage, teachers should give pupils sufficient time to practice and master the learning content before introducing a new state material.

Piaget was one of the first psychologists to make a systematic study of cognitive development. His contributions include a stage theory of child cognitive development, detailed observational studies of cognition in children, and a series of simple but ingenious tests to reveal different cognitive abilities. His ideas have been of practical use in understanding and communicating with children, particularly in the field of education (re: Discovery Learning). Piaget's theory of cognitive development explains how a child constructs a mental model of the world. He disagreed with the idea that intelligence was a fixed trait, and regarded cognitive development as a process which occurs due to biological maturation and interaction with the environment. The goal of the theory is to explain the mechanisms and processes by which the infant, and then the child, develops into an individual who can reason and think using hypotheses.

Piaget claimed that knowledge cannot simply emerge from sensory experience; some initial structure is necessary to make sense of the world. According to Piaget, children are born with a very basic mental structure (genetically inherited and evolved) on which all subsequent learning and knowledge are based (McLeod, 2022). He emphasized the importance of schemas in

cognitive development and described how they were developed or acquired. A schema can be defined as a set of linked mental representations of the world, which we use both to understand and to respond to situations. The assumption is that we store these mental representations and apply them when needed.

However, Piaget's principles and ideas have been criticized by scholars such as Vygotsky and Bruner who would rather not talk about cognitive development in stages at all, preferring to see development as a continuous process. Vygotsky, a contemporary of Piaget, argued that social interaction is crucial for cognitive development. According to Vygotsky the child's learning always occurs in a social context in co-operation with someone more skillful. This social interaction provides language opportunities and Vygotsky considered language the foundation of thought.

Again, Piaget (1952) did not explicitly relate his theory to education, although later researchers have explained how features of Piaget's theory can be applied to teaching and learning. Others have queried the age ranges of the stages. Some studies have shown that progress to the formal operational stage is not guaranteed. For example, Keating (1979) reported that 40-60% of college students fail at formal operation tasks, and Dasen (1994) states that only one-third of adults ever reach the formal operational stage. Because Piaget concentrated on the universal stages of cognitive development and biological maturation, he failed to consider the effect that the social setting and culture may have on cognitive development.

Hughes (1975), states that Piaget failed to distinguish between competence (what a child is capable of doing) and performance (what a child can show when given a particular task). When tasks are altered, performance (and therefore competence) is affected. Therefore, Piaget might have overestimated children's cognitive abilities. For example, a child might have object permanence (competence) but still not be able to search for objects (performance). In spite of all these, the influence of Piaget's ideas in developmental psychology has been enormous. He changed how people viewed the child's world and their methods of studying children. He inspired many who came after and took up his ideas thereby generating huge amount of research which has increased our understanding of cognitive development.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The education process provides children with opportunities of supported exploration and experimentation, intentional demonstration and instruction, as well as guided discovery. Hence, our conclusion is that applying Piaget's or any other theory of cognitive development can help parents, scholars, caregivers and guardians better understand the developmental stages and attributes of a child. Consequently, this paper therefore makes the following recommendations:

- i. *Both parents and caregivers should be sensitive to the development process of every child. Attention should be given to the different stages of growth of children so as to help them get acquainted with their environment.*
- ii. *Children should not be exposed to environmental and social hazards all of which has the capacity of negatively influencing the growth and development of a child. Parents*

- and teachers should be good role models knowing that children learn behavioural attributes from them.*
- iii. *Government should establish special educational facilities for children. These facilities will provide children with the needed educational and learning aids all of which will improve their cognitive development at every stage.*
- iv. *Learning should be activity-based with the school providing a lot of toys and other instructional materials that will engage the attention of pupils and stimulate their desire to learn.*

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